

Causes of Regurgitation and Vomiting Syndrome in Newborns

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Abstract: Vomiting is a complex neuroreflex action, vomiting in the medulla oblongata under the control of the front abdominal wall, diaphragm and stomach muscles is carried out using the floor. Vomiting is often caused by the digestive system it is considered a protective reaction and occurs as a result of tickling of the vomiting center will come The vomiting center is in the area of the reticular formation of the medulla oblongata It is located in the surrounding respiratory, cardiovascular, cough, and vegetative centers is inextricably linked. Therefore, this is the excitation of the vomiting center causes the centers to be affected (changes in breathing, tachycardia, salivation).

Key words: VOMITING, REGURGITATION, newborns, factors, defects.

1. Chemoreceptor trigger area: humoral affected by factors.
2. Higher center: vestibular system, cortex, thalamus, hypothalamus.
3. Vomiting center: central and peripheral afferent signals coordination, vomiting to be provoked.
4. Vagus afferent signals.

Peripheral area: gastrointestinal tract, pharynx, cardiovascular system, bile ways.

Figure 15. Vomiting center and its dependent areas.

Vomiting a small amount of stomach mass in the larynx and mouth passive return to space is understood.

Vomiting and vomiting often bother children of the first age, so they should go to the pediatrician is a condition that leads to referral for counseling. Statistical information, the incidence of vomiting in breast-fed children is 18%.

(France) to 20% (USA), and of children who see a pediatrician 40% (Australia). 67% of children under 4 months vomits once a day, and 23% of children are vomited by their parents they rate it as "anxiety".

Vomiting and vomiting in children of early age causes can be organic and functional. M.F. Korshunova according to data, vomiting and vomiting in children of the first age is 5.3% of cases with pylorostenosis, in 10.8% with pylorospasm and in 83.9% with cardiac opening, Lactase deficiency is explained by such factors as damage to the nervous system.

Organic causes are anatomical in some parts of the gastrointestinal tract associated with conduction disorders. This requires surgical correction conditions: developmental defects of the gastrointestinal tract, neuromuscular congenital pathology or acute conditions of the apparatus.

The occurrence of functional vomiting in children is enzymatic slowness of processes and structure of digestive organs (short or wide esophagus, anatomical narrowings and not well developed esophagus, stomach muscle layer is poorly developed). This Violation of eating technique, overeating, motility and inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, bacterial and include viral infections (otitis, meningitis, respiratory infections). Return and not only motor activity, but also secretory causes of vomiting, in particular hyper- and Hypoacid conditions are also different The main causes of nausea and vomiting Pylostenosis Congenital hypertrophic pyloric stenosis is a hereditary disease in which the stomach is pyloric part of it is a developmental defect. Vomiting in children will lead to Pathogenesis. In the disease, a sharp narrowing of the pyloric canal is observed. As a result persistent vomiting and metabolic changes appear. From the narrowed part above, the stomach expands, its walls are hypertrophied, in the mucous membrane and erosions may appear.

The incidence of congenital hypertrophic pylorostenosis is close relatives it was determined that it was related to the marriage between Family origin 6.9% identified in cases. The risk for brothers of a sick child is 4%, for sisters and it is 3%. The risk is relevant for the brothers and sisters of the sick girl 9% and 4% respectively. Population incidence rate 0.5:1000 - It is 3:1000. This disease is more common in boys Pylorospasm Pathogenesis. From birth in children with high excitability after feeding, vomiting with coagulated milk is observed.

A sharp contraction of the pyloric sphincter leads to the evacuation of food from the stomach destroys. Cardiac hypotonia and antiperistalsis occur, causes vomiting.

Esophageal chaliasia

Pathogenesis. Esophageal chalazion in the development of the nervous system of infants violation is included. This process is based on the esophagus and stomach, cardiac part lies in the violation of the development of innervation. Sympathetic ganglia in the cardiac part In a child born without development, the entrance to the stomach is not completely fixed and as a result esophageal-gastric failure occurs, parasympathetic part and in its deficiency, cardiospasm develops in babies.

Other organic causes of nausea and vomiting syndrome The reason for the return is found in a number of genetic syndromes esophageal atresia, congenital esophageal stenosis, and esophagitis may have diverticula. Esophageal atresia has a rate of 1 in 1000 is 0.3 per live birth. This disease has different forms, in particular, it also occurs with tracheo-esophageal fistula. Esophageal atresia should be identified in the maternity ward, and this defect requires immediate surgery.

Esophageal stenosis in the cervicothoracic location from birth then begins immediately, the child "gets food stuck" during each swallowing movement. Some symptoms of the disease appear at breast age or later. If if esophageal diverticula are located in its upper part, in large quantities belching with food mixed with mucus may be observed. Esophagus Esophagoscopy and x-ray examination are of great importance in diverticula and stenosis earns. Treatment is operative.

The cause of vomiting is esophageal bifurcation or congenital short esophagus it can. Vomiting, dysphagia, protein in the clinic of these diseases energy deficiency may develop. Often erosive esophagitis, an ulcer appears on the mucous membrane of the stomach, and in this case there is vomiting blood appears in the masses.

Clinical signs similar to the differential diagnosis of pylorostenosis is carried out with phrenopyloric syndrome. Based on this disease esophageal hiatal hernia of the diaphragm, chest of the stomach the transition to the cage and spastic contraction of the pyloric canal are observed. Phrenopyloric Vomiting similar to the clinic of pylorostenosis is also observed in the syndrome. Solution X-ray method serves as the next diagnostic method. Babies Diaphragmatic hernia requires urgent surgery. of the operation the essence is to return the organs that have moved to the chest to the abdominal cavity and will eliminate the defect in the diaphragm.

It should be mentioned that the intestine is a duodenum with developmental defects Congenital stenosis of the intestine and its anomalous blood vessel or ring compression by the pancreas, congenital pre-pyloric sphincter stenosis is also high Pylorostenosis, such as diseases that manifest the clinical appearance of intestinal obstruction similar to clinical signs. In each of these cases, the diagnosis is X-ray examination based on the results. The aforementioned birth defects unlike pylorostenosis, the appearance of vomiting from the 4-5th day of the child's life it is distinguished by the fact that there is constant grass in the vomit and masses.